

trend was detected, and in these cases, the null hypothesis (H₀) prevailed. The spatial distribution of the data shows the average air temperature values for each time series individually: a) Average annual air temperatures for the vegetation period in the observed area range from 10.6 °C in Dimitrovgrad to 18.1 °C in Belgrade; b) Average annual maximum air temperatures for the vegetation period range from 32.1 °C in Niš to 25.6 °C in Zlatibor; c) Average annual minimum air temperatures for the vegetation period range from -1 °C in Sjenica to 7.1 °C in Belgrade. These results provide an overview and understanding of climate changes in Central Serbia, identifying areas with increasing or decreasing air temperatures and offering a foundation for future research and climate strategies.

Keywords: climate change, Central Serbia, average annual temperature trends, vegetation period, Mann-Kendall trend test, GIS.

Qualitative insights into cultural heritage protection in Serbia: Evaluating legal and institutional gaps

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This research is dedicated to a comprehensive examination of the strengths and weaknesses inherent in the legal and institutional measures designed to protect cultural heritage in the Republic of Serbia from the adverse effects of natural disasters, including earthquakes, landslides, rockfalls, floods, torrents, storms, hail, and forest fires. The study aims to identify the primary challenges and shortcomings within the existing legal and institutional framework, while also pinpointing and analyzing best practices and potential improvements for the protection system. This research posits a preliminary hypothesis suggesting that challenges may exist within the legal and institutional framework for the protection of cultural heritage in the Republic of Serbia, potentially limiting effective response and recovery following natu-

ral disasters. This hypothesis will be further developed and adapted based on the analysis of available data. Data collection for this research was conducted through semi-structured interviews with experts and an in-depth analysis of existing documentation. By conducting interviews with experts in the field, the research seeks to gather critical data and insights that will enhance the understanding of these issues and contribute to formulating viable solutions. The analysis and processing of data were carried out using ATLAS.ti software, which facilitated a comprehensive and systematic examination of the collected qualitative information. Furthermore, an assessment of the current capacity of institutions to respond rapidly and effectively to natural disasters that pose a threat to cultural heritage is a key component of the study. The ultimate goal is to develop recommendations that will fortify the legal and institutional framework, thereby bolstering the resilience of cultural heritage sites in Serbia against future natural disasters. The results of the research, highlight significant deficiencies in the legal framework, inadequate institutional capacities and resources, as well as a lack of proper training for crisis response. The need for improved inter-institutional cooperation and the development of technical-logistical resources is emphasized. This paper represents a significant contribution to the understanding and enhancement of the cultural heritage protection system, providing a foundation for further research and strategy development in this area.

Keywords: disasters; hazards; cultural heritage; protecting; qualitative research; interview; Serbia.

Advancing urban sustainability: Applying geospatial technologies to assess SDG indicators – A case study of Podgorica (Montenegro)

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This paper investigates the application of a model for calculating Sustainable development goal (SDG) indicator 11.7.1 using the example of Podgorica (Montenegro). Indicator 11.7.1 measures the proportion of open public spa-